

Development And Validation of Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC And LC-MS/MS Methods For Quantification of Eltrombopag Olamine and Carbidopa-Levodopa Impurities

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ABSTRACT

Robust and sensitive analytical methods were developed and validated for the simultaneous quantification of Eltrombopag Olamine (ELO) and its related impurities, alongside Carbidopa and Levodopa impurities in pharmaceutical formulations. An RP-HPLC method employing a Cosmisil Phenyl-Hexyl column was optimized for ELO and its contaminants, while an LC-MS/MS method was established for the nitrosamine impurity N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)nitrous amide (NDELA) quantification. For Carbidopa and Levodopa impurities, an RP-HPLC method using a Kromasil column was developed. Method optimization utilized a Quality by Design (QbD) approach with factorial design experiments to ensure robustness. Validation parameters, including specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ), complied with ICH guidelines. Forced degradation studies confirmed the stability-indicating nature of the methods. The validated techniques demonstrated high sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility, making them suitable for routine quality control and stability testing of pharmaceutical products containing ELO, Carbidopa, and Levodopa.

Keywords: Eltrombopag Olamine, Carbidopa, Levodopa, RP-HPLC, LC-MS/MS, Nitrosamine, NDELA, Method Validation, Quality by Design, Stability-Indicating Method

INTRODUCTION

Eltrombopag Olamine (ELO) is a thrombopoietin receptor agonist used primarily for treating thrombocytopenia. Accurate assay and impurity profiling are essential to ensure drug safety and efficacy. Although pharmacokinetic studies involving HPLC, LC/MS, and UPLC-MS exist, comprehensive stability-indicating methods developed using a Quality by Design (QbD) framework are lacking. The presence of nitrosamine impurities, such as N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl)nitrous amide (NDELA), a Category 2 carcinogen, necessitates sensitive and specific quantification methods.

Carbidopa and Levodopa are commonly co-administered in Parkinson's disease therapy, with impurities potentially affecting therapeutic outcomes. Therefore, developing simultaneous quantification

methods for these impurities using RP-HPLC is critical for quality control.

This study aims to develop and validate stability-indicating RP-HPLC methods⁴ for ELO and Carbidopa-Levodopa impurities and an LC-MS/MS method for NDELA quantification, incorporating factorial design and risk assessment to ensure method robustness and regulatory compliance².

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and Reagents

Eltrombopag Olamine and related impurities were sourced from Granules India (Hyderabad, India). Potassium dihydrogen phosphate was procured from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). HPLC-grade methanol, orthophosphoric acid, and acetonitrile were obtained from Rankem (India). Milli-Q water was used

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throughout the study. Carbidopa, Levodopa, Entacapone, and their impurities were acquired from Divis Laboratories Ltd. and Aurobindo Pharma. Methanol, acetonitrile, and phosphoric acid were purchased from Merck India.

2.2 Analytical Conditions

2.2.1 Eltrombopag Olamine Related Substances Method:

Parameter	Condition
Column	Cosmisil Phenyl-Hexyl, 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 3.5 μm
Mobile Phase A	3.72 g/L potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer: acetonitrile (90:10, v/v), pH 3.5 ± 0.2 (adjusted with OPA)
Mobile Phase B	Water, methanol, acetonitrile (10:20:70, v/v)
Flow Rate	1.2 mL/min
Injection Volume	20 μL
Column Temperature	45°C
Detector	PDA at 230 nm
Pump Mode	Gradient elution

a. Blank Preparation: Diluent composed of degassed water: methanol (50:50 v/v), selected based on ELO

solubility and stability. Glassware was rinsed with diluent prior to use (Figure 01)

Figure 01: Blank preparation (Diluent) chromatogram

b. Standard Preparation: 38.3 mg ELO (equivalent to 30 mg base) dissolved in 160 mL diluent by sonication, diluted to 250 mL, then further diluted as required (Figure 02)

c. Sample Preparation: Ten tablets (~75 mg each) extracted sequentially with 200 mL water (shaken 45

Figure 02: Standard solution chromatogram

min at 160 rpm), then 200 mL methanol (shaken 15 min), cooled to room temperature, diluted with 200 mL diluent, sonicated 20 min below room

temperature, centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min, filtered, and diluted appropriately for analysis (Figure 03)

Figure 03: Sample solution chromatogram

2.2.2 Nitrosamine (NDELA) Analysis

Parameter	Condition
Column	ACE AR C-18, 100 × 4.6 mm, 3 μm
Mobile Phase A	0.1% formic acid in water
Mobile Phase B	100% methanol
Flow Rate	0.5 mL/min
Injection Volume	50 μL
Column Temperature	40°C
Sampler Temperature	5°C
Mass Spectrometry	Positive ESI mode, MRM scan
Source Parameters	CUR 40, IS 5500, CAD 8, TEM 550, GS1 55, GS2 60
Compound Parameters	DP 33.5, EP 13, CE 16.5, CXP 5
MRM Transition	Q1 mass 135 → Q3 mass 74, dwell time 200 ms

Stock and standard solutions were prepared in methanol and diluent as described. LC-MS/MS spectra shown in Figure 04

Figure 04: NDELA LC-MS/MS spectra

2.2.3 Carbidopa and Levodopa Impurities Method:

Parameter	Condition
Column	Kromasil 100 Å, 250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm
Mobile Phase A	20 mM potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer, pH 3.8
Mobile Phase B	Water and methanol (20:80, v/v)
Flow Rate	1.0 mL/min
Injection Volume	10 µL
Column Temperature	25°C
Detector	PDA at 220 nm
Pump Mode	Gradient elution

a. Standard solutions prepared by dissolving 20 mg Carbidopa and 80 mg Levodopa in methanol:0.1 N HCl (75:25, v/v) diluted to 200 mL (final concentrations: 100 ppm Carbidopa, 400 ppm

Levodopa). Sample prepared by dissolving 100 mg tablet powder in 120 mL dissolving phase, shaken 60 min at 150 rpm, diluted to 200 mL, filtered (Figure 05).

Figure 05: Graphical representation of analytical conditions

2.3 Method Development and OptimizationA. Eltrombopag Olamine:

A buffer pH range of 2.0–4.5 was explored, with pH 3.5 selected to avoid peak merging and broad peaks at higher pH (Figure 06). The Phenyl-Hexyl column provided superior peak shape and resolution over C8, C18, and Phenyl columns (Figures 07, 08). The detection wavelength was optimized at 230 nm for impurity sensitivity. A factorial design (3 factors, 2 levels) evaluated effects of mobile phase composition, pH, and temperature on retention and resolution (Tables 01). A full factorial design (2^3) was employed to evaluate the influence of mobile phase composition

(acetonitrile content in MP-A and MP-B), pH, and column temperature on chromatographic performance. Eight experimental runs along with three center points were conducted to assess retention behavior, peak resolution, and tailing characteristics of ELO and its related impurities. The results demonstrated that increases in acetonitrile concentration and temperature significantly reduced retention times, while adequate resolution (>1.5) and acceptable tailing factors (≤ 1.5) were maintained across all experimental conditions, confirming the robustness of the developed method within the studied design space.

Figure 06: pH vs Retention time of Eltrombopag and nearby eluting peaks

Figure 07: ELO Chromatogram at 230 nm during development

Figure 08: ELO Chromatogram at 254 nm during development

Table 01- Summary of 2³ Factorial Design and Chromatographic Responses

Run	Code	% ACN MP-A	% ACN MP-B	Temp (°C)	Rt ELO (min)	Rt Imp-3 (min)	Rt Imp-7 (min)	Resolution (ELO-Imp-4)	Min Resolution*	Tailing Factor (ELO)
1	1	5	65	40	17.338	15.652	22.116	8.43	1.87	1.01
2	A	15	65	40	14.624	12.860	19.987	8.14	1.95	1.01
3	B	5	75	40	14.372	11.975	17.621	7.25	1.81	1.03
4	C	5	65	50	16.072	14.463	20.834	7.61	1.83	0.98
5	AB	15	75	40	10.790	9.466	15.326	6.47	1.83	1.04
6	AC	15	65	50	14.269	11.640	18.536	7.15	1.88	0.98
7	BC	5	75	50	12.283	10.965	16.493	6.57	1.77	0.99
8	ABC	15	75	50	9.734	8.537	14.126	5.65	1.75	1.00
9	Center-1	10	70	45	14.354	11.842	18.066	7.29	1.86	1.00
10	Center-2	10	70	45	14.344	11.834	18.057	7.32	1.86	1.00
11	Center-3	10	70	45	14.342	11.832	18.570	7.30	1.86	1.00

*Minimum resolution observed among adjacent critical peaks (Imp-5/Imp-6).

B. NDELA:LC-MS/MS method development addressed solubility and color challenges of ELO

API. Achieved LOQ below 3 ppm to meet regulatory limits for this carcinogenic impurity. Gradient elution and column selection optimized for specificity and sensitivity (Table 02).

Table 02. Gradient program for NDELA

Time	% A	% B
0	96	4
2	96	4
10	4	96
20	4	96
20.1	96	4
25	96	4

C. Carbidopa-Levodopa:

Method development considered pKa values and buffer pH. Initial trials with Reprisil ODS column showed insufficient resolution. Kromasil column with pH 4.8 phosphate buffer and gradient elution

improved separation and peak shape, with detection at 220 nm enhancing impurity response. QbD approach with fractional factorial design identified buffer pH and flow rate as critical parameters (Figure 09, Tables 03).

Figure 09: Chromatogram in final method conditions

Table 03. QbD Approach Using Fractional Factorial Design for Identification of Critical Method Parameters

QbD Element	Description Based on DoE Results
Analytical Target Profile (ATP)	To achieve consistent chromatographic performance with adequate resolution, controlled retention behavior, and acceptable system suitability for all responses (R-1, R-2, and R-3).
Experimental Design	Fractional factorial design evaluating three method parameters at selected levels (Table 4.101).
Method Parameters Evaluated	A: Buffer pH (4.2–4.8) B: Flow rate (0.8–1.2 mL/min) C: Column temperature (20–30 °C)
Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs)	R-1, R-2, and R-3 (chromatographic responses).

Statistical Tool	Analysis	Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for factorial model (Table 4.102).
Significant Identified	Factors	Buffer pH (A) – significant effect on R-1 ($p = 0.0160$) and R-3 ($p = 0.0034$). Flow rate (B) – significant effect on R-1 ($p = 0.0026$), R-2 ($p = 0.0002$), and R-3 ($p = 0.0034$).
Non-Critical Parameter		Column temperature (C) – not statistically significant across responses ($p > 0.05$).
Critical Parameters (CMPs)	Method	Buffer pH and Flow rate
Risk Outcome	Assessment	Buffer pH and flow rate classified as high-risk parameters due to significant influence on CQAs; column temperature classified as low-risk within the studied range.
QbD Conclusion		The fractional factorial DoE successfully identified buffer pH and flow rate as CMPs, forming the basis for design space establishment and robust method control.

2.4 Forced Degradation and Specificity Studies

A. Eltrombopag Olamine:

Forced degradation under acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic conditions revealed ELO

stability under thermal, photolytic, and neutral hydrolysis, but degradation under acidic and oxidative stress (Table 04, Figures 10-15). Mass balance was maintained, confirming specificity.

Table 04. ELO Forced degradation values

Nature of Stress	Stress Conditions	% Impurities	% Assay	% Mass Balance	PA (Purity Angle)	PT (Purity Threshold)	PF
Actual / Initial	NA	0.06	98.8	98.9	0.367	0.570	Pass
Acidic stress	0.5 N HCl for 6 h at 60 °C	0.07	96.4	96.5	0.039	0.461	Pass
Basic stress	0.5 N NaOH for 1 h at 60 °C	0.13	98.5	98.6	0.038	0.469	Pass
Peroxide stress	5% H ₂ O ₂ at RT for 4 h	10.70	88.5	99.2	0.037	0.375	Pass
Photolytic stress	1200 W·m ⁻² , 200 million lux·h	0.06	99.1	99.2	0.406	0.611	Pass
Thermal stress	80% RH for 24 h	0.07	98.1	98.2	0.040	0.476	Pass

PA – Purity Angle; PT – Purity Threshold; PF – Purity Flag

Figure 10: ELO Acid sample chromatogram

Figure 11: ELO base sample chromatogram

Figure 12: ELO Oxidation Chromatogram

Figure 13: ELO Thermal Chromatogram

Figure 14: ELO Photolytic Chromatogram

Figure 15: Chromatogram of ELO with all Impurity mixture

B. Carbidopa-Levodopa:

Carbidopa degraded under acidic, basic, and oxidative stress, while Levodopa remained stable. Thermal, humidity, and photolytic stress showed no degradation for either compound. The method separated degradation products effectively, confirming specificity.

2.5 Validation

2.5.1 Linearity:

ELO and impurities showed linearity from LOQ to 150% of specification with $R^2 > 0.997$ (Tables 05). Carbidopa-Levodopa impurities showed $R^2 = 0.999$ over tested range.

Table 05. Summary of Linearity Results for ELO and Related Impurities

Analyte	Linearity Range (ppm)	No. of Levels	Regression Equation ($y = mx + c$)	Correlation Coefficient (R^2)	Y-bias at Specification Level (%)
ELO Impurity-1	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 77024.66x + 1524.23$	0.9993	6.18
ELO Impurity-2	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 78064.52x + 62.91$	0.9979	0.28
Impurity-3	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 80224.42x + 1080.26$	0.9999	4.30
Impurity-4	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 91380.43x + 1037.74$	0.9993	4.74
Impurity-5	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 93400.71x + 774.32$	0.9990	2.85
Impurity-6	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 84794.69x + 131.15$	0.9993	0.53
Impurity-7	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 83410.92x - 51.57$	0.9991	-0.21
ELO	LOQ – 150%	7	$y = 96295.65x + 1138.43$	0.9992	4.67

2.5.2 Precision:

robustness (Tables 06). Carbidopa-Levodopa precision was within acceptable limits.

Repeatability and intermediate precision for ELO impurities had %RSD < 5%, demonstrating

Table 06. Summary of Precision Results for ELO Related Impurities

Impurity	Precision Type	Mean (%)	Std. Deviation	%RSD
Impurity-1	Repeatability	0.189	0.005	2.63
	Intermediate precision	0.190	0.006	4.16
	Between analysts	0.189	0.005	2.81
Impurity-2	Repeatability	0.187	0.002	0.87
	Intermediate precision	0.191	0.005	2.60
	Between analysts	0.189	0.004	2.19
Impurity-3	Repeatability	0.192	0.006	4.18
	Intermediate precision	0.188	0.005	2.81
	Between analysts	0.190	0.006	4.11
Impurity-4	Repeatability	0.198	0.007	4.69
	Intermediate precision	0.202	0.006	4.22
	Between analysts	0.200	0.007	4.42
Impurity-5	Repeatability	0.186	0.006	4.49
	Intermediate precision	0.194	0.004	2.22
	Between analysts	0.190	0.007	4.62
Impurity-6	Repeatability	0.208	0.004	1.80
	Intermediate precision	0.210	0.008	4.71
	Between analysts	0.209	0.006	2.86
Impurity-7	Repeatability	0.206	0.005	2.40
	Intermediate precision	0.209	0.005	2.59
	Between analysts	0.207	0.005	2.51

2.5.3 Accuracy:

Recovery for ELO impurities ranged 92–107% (Tables 07). Carbidopa-Levodopa impurities showed 91.2–108.2% recovery.

Table 07. Summary of Accuracy (Recovery) Results for ELO Related Impurities

Impurity	Accuracy Level	Concentration Range (ppm)	No. of Determinations	Mean % Recovery	Recovery Range (%)	Acceptance Criteria
Impurity-1	LOQ	~0.036	6	102.2	100.3–104.1	80–120
	100%	~0.239	3	102.9	101.7–104.7	90–110
	150%	~0.359	6	104.7	101.6–107.2	90–110
Impurity-2	LOQ	~0.036	6	97.1	92.1–99.2	80–120
	100%	~0.239	3	98.9	97.8–100.8	90–110
	150%	~0.359	6	96.3	92.0–99.7	90–110
Impurity-3	LOQ	~0.036	6	97.9	97.4–98.7	80–120
	100%	~0.241	3	99.9	98.1–100.9	90–110
	150%	~0.361	6	98.1	97.5–99.0	90–110
Impurity-4	LOQ	~0.035	6	99.9	99.2–100.2	80–120
	100%	~0.236	3	99.0	98.6–99.7	90–110
	150%	~0.354	6	99.9	98.8–100.5	90–110
Impurity-5	LOQ	~0.035	6	98.6	96.1–105.0	80–120
	100%	~0.232	3	97.3	95.4–99.0	90–110
	150%	~0.348	6	99.6	97.6–101.8	90–110
Impurity-6	LOQ	~0.034	6	101.4	96.4–105.7	80–120
	100%	~0.228	3	104.0	101.9–105.2	90–110
	150%	~0.341	6	101.5	97.7–105.2	90–110
Impurity-7	LOQ	~0.036	6	105.6	104.0–108.8	80–120
	100%	~0.238	3	102.5	101.3–104.9	90–110
	150%	~0.357	6	100.7	97.3–104.3	90–110

2.5.4 LOD and LOQ:

ELO impurities had LOQ < 0.036 ppm. NDELA LC-MS/MS LOQ was 2.99 ppm. Carbidopa-Levodopa impurities had sufficiently low LOQ values. The LOQ values for ELO and its related impurities were below 0.036 ppm, indicating excellent method sensitivity.

The LC-MS/MS method for NDELA demonstrated adequate sensitivity with an LOQ of **2.99 ppm**, acceptable linearity ($R^2 = 0.9989$), and satisfactory accuracy and precision. Overall, the results comply with ICH Q2(R1) requirements and confirm suitability of the methods for trace-level impurity determination.

Table 08. Summary of LOD, LOQ, and Method Validation Results

Analyte	Technique	Slope	Correction Factor	LOD (ppm)	LOQ (ppm)	R ²
Impurity-1	HPLC	77024.66	1.25	0.012	0.036	—
Impurity-2	HPLC	78064.52	1.23	0.012	0.036	—
Impurity-3	HPLC	80224.42	1.20	0.012	0.036	—
Impurity-4	HPLC	91380.43	1.05	0.012	0.035	—
Impurity-5	HPLC	93400.71	1.03	0.012	0.035	—
Impurity-6	HPLC	84794.69	1.14	0.011	0.034	—

Impurity-7	HPLC	83410.92	1.15	0.012	0.036	—
ELO	HPLC	96295.65	1.00	0.012	0.035	—
NDELA	LC-MS/MS	15056.5	—	1.20	2.99	0.9989

2.5.5 Robustness:

Design of experiments confirmed method robustness; resolution >1.5 maintained under variable conditions (Tables 09).

Table 09. Summary of Robustness Evaluation Using Design of Experiments

Parameter	Experimental Variation Studied	Observed Range	Acceptance Criteria	Robustness Outcome
% Acetonitrile in MP-A	5 – 15 %	Varied across DoE runs	As per method	No adverse impact
% Acetonitrile in MP-B	65 – 75 %	Varied across DoE runs	As per method	No adverse impact
Column Temperature	40 – 50 °C	Varied across DoE runs	As per method	No adverse impact
Retention time (min)	Imp-1 to Imp-7 & ELO	2.23 – 22.12 min	Consistent elution	Acceptable
Resolution between peaks	Adjacent peaks	1.75 – 36.64	≥ 1.5	Complies
Critical resolution (Imp-5 / Imp-6)	Most sensitive pair	≥ 1.75	≥ 1.5	Complies
Tailing factor	All impurities & ELO	0.91 – 1.40	≤ 2.0	Complies
System suitability consistency	Center point runs (n = 3)	Comparable RT, Rs, TF	Consistent	Stable
Overall DoE outcome	Combined factor interaction	No significant effect	—	Method robust

2.6 Risk Assessment and Control Strategy**A. Risk Assessment and Control Strategy**

In the development and validation of RP-HPLC methods for the analysis of Eltrombopag Olamine (ELO) and its related substances, critical parameters influencing method performance were identified

through systematic risk assessment. Among these, mobile phase preparation and chromatographic conditions emerged as critical due to the challenge of close peak elution and the need for adequate resolution between analytes and impurities.

2.6.1 Risk Assessment Summary**Table 10 Risk assessment of method parameters**

Sr. No	Method Attribute	Parameters Affecting	Risk Level	Justification
1	Chromatographic conditions	Robustness, Specificity, Chromatography	Medium	Many peaks elute very closely, making resolution sensitive to chromatographic parameters.
2	Mobile phase preparation	Peak separation	High	Resolution values were found close to the critical threshold (~2.0), indicating high risk.

2.6.2. Control Strategy

Sr. No	Control Variable	Final Conditions	Details
1	Mobile phase preparation	Strict adherence to preparation protocols	Mobile phase preparation is critical to achieving consistent peak separation; minor deviations can impact resolution adversely.
2	System suitability testing	Inclusion of resolution evaluation in routine analysis	System suitability solutions must be analyzed regularly to confirm resolution between adjacent peaks remains above 2.0.

2.6.3 Supporting Data

A. Resolution Values: The resolution between critical peak pairs, such as ELO Impurity-4 and Impurity-5,

consistently ranged between 1.87 and 1.95 under various experimental conditions, highlighting the narrow margin for acceptable separation (Table 4.94 and Table 4.94 Resolution of peaks in experiments).

Table 11. Summary of Retention Time and Resolution of Peaks across Experiments (n = 11)

Peak	Retention Time (min) Mean \pm SD	Retention Time Range (min)	Resolution Mean \pm SD	Resolution Range
Imp-1	2.36 \pm 0.08	2.23 – 2.50	NA	NA
Imp-2	4.66 \pm 0.22	4.22 – 4.92	6.47 \pm 0.77	4.90 – 7.80
Imp-3	11.55 \pm 2.03	8.54 – 15.65	30.82 \pm 4.13	24.63 – 36.64
ELO	14.23 \pm 2.20	9.73 – 17.34	7.11 \pm 0.90	5.65 – 8.43
Imp-4	15.57 \pm 2.33	11.92 – 19.88	11.81 \pm 0.74	10.66 – 12.95
Imp-5	15.94 \pm 2.45	12.28 – 20.25	1.84 \pm 0.06	1.75 – 1.95
Imp-6	16.74 \pm 2.09	14.09 – 21.01	4.44 \pm 0.43	4.01 – 4.94
Imp-7	18.07 \pm 2.21	14.13 – 22.12	5.49 \pm 0.28	5.11 – 5.98

B. Design of Experiments (DoE):

The factorial design experiments confirmed that mobile phase composition and chromatographic parameters significantly affect resolution, the factorial design experiments confirmed that mobile phase composition and chromatographic parameters,

particularly buffer pH and flow rate, significantly influence resolution, while column temperature showed a comparatively lesser effect. The DoE approach effectively identified critical method parameters and demonstrated the robustness of the developed chromatographic method.

Table 12. Summary of Design of Experiments (DoE) and Statistical Evaluation

Category	Description
Experimental Design	Full factorial design with center points
Number of Experiments	15 runs (including 3 center point replicates)
Factors Studied	A: Buffer pH (4.2–4.8) B: Flow rate (0.8–1.2 mL/min) C: Column temperature (20–30 °C)
Mobile Phase Composition	MP-A: 5–15% Acetonitrile MP-B: 65–75% Acetonitrile
Responses Evaluated	R1, R2, R3 (chromatographic resolution parameters)

Range of Responses	R1: 1.78 – 2.31 R2: 1.60 – 2.08 R3: 4.42 – 4.72
Significant Factors (ANOVA)	R1: Buffer pH (A), Flow rate (B) R2: Flow rate (B) R3: Buffer pH (A), Flow rate (B)
Non-significant Factor	Column temperature (C) for R2 and R3
Model Significance ($p < 0.05$)	All selected factorial models significant for R1, R2, and R3
Lack of Fit	Significant for R1 and R2 Not significant for R3
Overall Outcome	Mobile phase composition (buffer pH and acetonitrile content) and flow rate have a significant influence on chromatographic resolution, confirming robustness and criticality of method parameters

C. System Suitability Test Results: The system limits, but the close elution of peaks necessitates suitability testing showed theoretical plates, stringent control. symmetry, and resolution values within acceptable

Table 13. System Suitability Test (SST) Results for ELO and Related Impurities

Name of Analyte	Other Name	RT (min)	Resolution	Theoretical Plates	Symmetry Factor	%RSD
Impurity-1	ELO-2 / Amino impurity	2.363	NA	4,609	1.24	2.06
Impurity-2	ELO-3 / Pyrazole impurity	4.805	6.53	4,516	1.08	4.55
Impurity-3	Amide impurity	11.842	31.33	50,363	1.40	4.42
ELO	Main peak	14.354	7.29	68,117	1.00	2.77
Impurity-4	N-Oxide impurity	15.789	12.01	98,002	1.04	1.93
Impurity-5	Methoxy impurity	16.163	1.86	103,401	1.04	1.99
Impurity-6	Methyl ester impurity	16.968	4.02	115,609	1.04	4.56
Impurity-7	Ethyl ester impurity	18.066	5.58	137,741	1.05	4.51

The criticality of mobile phase preparation is underscored by the proximity of peak elution times, which directly impacts the resolution and accuracy of impurity quantification. The chromatographic conditions, including buffer composition, pH, flow rate, and temperature, were optimized using a robust DoE approach to maintain resolution above the

threshold of 2.0. However, the narrow resolution margin classifies mobile phase preparation as a high-risk parameter, requiring strict procedural adherence. Routine system suitability testing focusing on resolution metrics is imperative for ongoing method reliability, ensuring that any drift in chromatographic performance is promptly detected and corrected.

(A)

Figure 16: DoE graphs (A,B,C)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The RP-HPLC method for ELO achieved baseline separation of seven known impurities with excellent resolution and peak symmetry. Forced degradation studies confirmed the method's stability-indicating capability. The LC-MS/MS method provided sensitive, specific quantification of NDELA, meeting regulatory requirements. The Carbidopa-Levodopa RP-HPLC method successfully separated impurities with acceptable resolution, precision, and accuracy, supported by a QbD-based design space.

CONCLUSION

Validated RP-HPLC and LC-MS/MS methods provide reliable, sensitive, and specific quantification of Eltrombopag Olamine, its impurities, and NDELA nitrosamine, as well as Carbidopa and Levodopa impurities. Incorporation of a Quality by Design approach and factorial design ensured method robustness and reproducibility. The methods comply with ICH guidelines and are suitable for routine quality control and stability testing in pharmaceutical analysis, ensuring product safety and efficacy.

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